

Spiritual Growth and Learning is a Life-Long Adventure

Mark 4:26-29

²⁶ And He was saying, "The kingdom of God is like a man who casts seed upon the soil; ²⁷ and he goes to bed at night and gets up by day, and the seed sprouts and grows—how, he himself does not know.

²⁸ "The soil produces crops by itself; first the blade, then the head, then the mature grain in the head.

²⁹ "But when the crop permits, he immediately puts in the sickle, because the harvest has come."

Parables can take on many different interpretations. One way to examine this parable is that Yeshua was talking about spiritual growth. Yeshua met many people during His ministry, and they immediately followed Him. Why? They determined that Yeshua was the Messiah that the LORD had promised to His people.

Nevertheless, did they remain as disciples? That is an impossible question to answer. Indeed, many of them did because the faith grew. Many probably did not. Yeshua was only with them for three years. How long does it take for spiritual growth to occur? It is a unique process for every individual. Similarities will exist between people. However, there is a uniqueness to spiritual development (growth).

Spiritual growth starts with a seed being planted. The seed is a metaphor for the idea that there is a need to come to know the LORD. That seed can be a basic understanding of the work of Yeshua. Today many people would have to commence their spiritual growth with a seed that convinces them that the LORD does exist. In Yeshua's day, that would not have been necessary. Today that situation exists for many people.

Spiritual growth can then occur by the study of the Bible, especially an understanding of the Gospels. It may be necessary for a mentor to help. In the parable, the farmer does not intervene to help the crop grow. However, the seeds do receive help from the soil. It contains the nutrients and water necessary for growth. Therefore, it can be

concluded that a mentor is necessary for spiritual growth. The soil is the spiritual mentor. Then the farmer is not necessarily a person. The farmer can be a metaphor for an event or feeling that sparks a person to learn about the LORD.

When is spiritual growth over? The answer is never. Unfortunately, many people today are not interested in continual spiritual growth. They get baptized and are satisfied. Many times a person comes to understand Yeshua, gets baptized, then never enters the church again. They believe that they have obtained salvation through baptism. However, that is not the truth. Baptism is only the beginning of the spiritual journey. Suppose the harvest is a metaphor for the completion of one's spiritual growth. In that case, the harvest is the disconnection from the LORD. When the sickle cuts the crop, all growth stops. Therefore, the crop should never tell the farmer that it is ready to be harvested. Why? Because the harvest of a crop is the crop's death. Spiritual growth must never be halted!

The Scripture is as deep as the LORD is infinite. Based on this, spiritual growth and learning never conclude. There is always more to learn. Using the parable metaphorically, the crop harvest never happens. If the soil is a metaphor for the LORD, then a harvest is a disconnection from the LORD. This situation is not a desirable event. The parable says that it is up to the crop to decide to harvest.

Several metaphors have been introduced in this examination. As one reads the parable, there are more ways to view it. This examination considers the parable to be about spiritual growth. The idea of learning everything about the LORD can take hold in a person. It will occur differently in each person. It will take a different amount of time for each person. Yeshua said that it would occur. The crop is the spiritual awareness of the individual. Once the growth starts, it should never be stopped because there is an

infinite amount of learning about the LORD that has to be done. It is a life long adventure.

May the LORD bless you in your learning and studying of His Word.